

Shanlax International Journal of Management

NATIONAL CONFERENCE ON

**“EMERGING TRENDS ON ENTREPRENEURIAL
OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES”**

(NCEOOC - 2016)

(A Peer - Reviewed - Refereed / Scholarly Quarterly Journal with Impact Factor)

Vol. 4

Special Issue 1

October 2016

ISSN: 2321 - 4643

Organized by

DEPARTMENT OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION

DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE

DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE WITH CA

CAUSSANEL COLLEGE OF ARTS AND SCIENCE

(Affiliated to Alagappa University, Karaikudi)

(Run by the Congregation of the Brothers of the Sacred Heart of Jesus, Palayamkottai)

Muthupettai – 623523

38	Global Online Entrepreneurship P.Ranjitha & Dr. A. Jayakumar	190
39	Challenges and New Innovation of Successful Entrepreneur Mrs. S.Lakshmi	194
40	Challenges and Opportunities in Indian Rural Entrepreneur Mrs. S.Nithya	200
41	Entrepreneurial Support and Development of SMEs through Incubators S.Sabithadevi	204
42	Roll of Women Entrepreneurship Through Self Help Group in Tamilnadu T.Sathya Devi & Dr. P. Amarjothi	207
43	Entrepreneurial Success of Mc Donald - A Critical Strategic Analytical Approach Dr. N. Shankar & C. Shalini	211
44	Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Organisational Commitment of College Teachers in Coimbatore P. Sripal & Dr. T. Paramasivan	217
45	Evolution of Women Education in India K.Sujatha	220
46	A Study on Problems Faced by Women's Entrepreneurs in India Mr.S.David Maria Tony	223
47	An Impact of Employer Branding Image on Banking Sector Employees with Special Reference to Sivagangai District Mrs.V.Vijayalakshmi & Dr.K.Udhayasuriyan	230
48	Global Entrepreneurship - Opportunities and Challenges P.Vathsala & M.Soumiya	234
49	Tourism Entrepreneurship Dr. S. Nagavalli	239
50	Working of Self Help Groups in Ramanathapuram Districts V. Sasireka	242
51	Women Entrepreneurship in India - Problems and Prospects M.Manikandan	246
52	Time Management of Banking, Insurance and Hospital in Industries N.Sakila	251
53	Prospects of Women Entrepreneurs in India Md.Ghouse Mohiddin Khan, Karthik & Hari Babu	254
54	A Study on Prospects and Challenges of Rural Entrepreneurship in India C.Udhaya Moorthi & V. Muneeswaran	258
55	Challenges and Opportunities of Woman Entrepreneur in India M.Bhuvanewari	263
56	A Study on Women Entrepreneurs Problems in India Dr. A. Dharmendran & Dr. P. Kannapiran	269

A STUDY ON WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS PROBLEMS IN INDIA

Dr. A. Dharmendran

Assistant Professor of Commerce, Caussanel College of Arts and Science, Muthupettai - 623 523

Dr. P. Kannapiran

Assistant Professor of Commerce, Government Arts College, Udthagamandalam-643 002

Abstract

The role of women entrepreneur in economic development is also being recognized and steps are being taken to promote women entrepreneurship. Resurgence of entrepreneurship is the need of the hour emphasizing on educating women strata of population, spreading awareness and consciousness amongst women to outshine in the enterprise field, making them realize their strengths, and important position in the society and the great contribution they can make for their industry as well as the entire economy. Women owned businesses are highly increasing in the economies of almost all countries. In India, although women constitute the half of the total population, the entrepreneurial world is still a male dominated one. Women in advanced nations are recognized and are more prominent in the business world. But the Indian women entrepreneurs are facing some major constraints. Development of women entrepreneurship is an essential part of human resource development. Compared to other countries the development of women entrepreneurship is very low in India, especially in the rural areas. Income generating activities are not merely viewed as a tool for economic needs of women. It is equally a powerful instrument to enable women to determine their own lives. Women are culturally well equipped to run their business due to skill developed through managing households, raising children etc. Therefore, shift from family management to enterprise management may be easier than a shift from paid employment to self-employment. This article focuses on the nature and status of women entrepreneurs in India. In the next part the problems of women entrepreneurs encountered and in last part some government schemes supporting to women entrepreneurs and suggestive measures to overcome the problems women entrepreneurs in India.

Keyword: *Entrepreneurship development, EDP, Women Entrepreneur, Entrepreneurship, Problems, Government Schemes, Measures*

Introduction

A women entrepreneur is “An enterprise owned and controlled by a women having a minimum financial interest of 51 percent of capital and giving at least 51 percent of the employment generated by the enterprise to women (Government of India).” Therefore, a women entrepreneur is a woman or group of women who initiate, organize and run a business enterprise. Women entrepreneurship is the process where women organize a business or industry and provide employment opportunities to others. A small enterprise is one where the investment limit does not exceed rupees five core. Women entrepreneurs may be defined as the women or a group of women who initiate, organize and operate a business enterprise. Entrepreneurship among women is an important avenue through which women can overcome their subordination within the family and the society as a whole. Therefore, development of entrepreneurship among women has received special attention of the policy makers. The new industrial policy has stressed the need for conducting special Entrepreneurial Development Programme (EDPs) for women, creates entrepreneurial awareness among them. Besides this, today, a network of institutions exists in the country to promote women entrepreneurship. Women owned businesses are highly increasing in the economies of almost all countries. In India, women constitute around 48 percent of the population but their participation in the economic activities is only 34 percent. The entrepreneurial world is still a male dominated one. Entrepreneurship is one of the important factors of industrialization playing an important role in the economic development of a country. As compared to men, women are less motivated to start business units due to some unwanted fear, lack of motivation and kind of activities.

Research Objectives

The main objectives of the present study are:

- To study the role of women entrepreneurs in India
- To study the nature of women entrepreneurs in India.
- To find out the problems encountered by women entrepreneurs.
- To review policies and schemes for women entrepreneurs in India
- To suggest the measures for success of women entrepreneurs in India.

Role of Women Entrepreneurs

The following chart explains the role of women entrepreneurs

Role of Women Entrepreneurs

The Nature Status of Entrepreneurship in India

Over the centuries, the notion of 'entrepreneur' and 'entrepreneurship' has been used in various senses. Conventionally, entrepreneurship has been considered as an inborn trait of the individual. In the Middle Ages entrepreneur was a 'person who was active and got things done'. In the 16th Century it describes those who risked their lives and fortunes in Wars. In 17th and 18th century it denotes those who risked their wealth in a business enterprise or financial contracts. Women entrepreneurs are key players in any developing country particularly in terms of their contribution to economic development. Women entrepreneurship has been recognized as an important source of economic growth. Women entrepreneurs create new jobs for themselves and others also. However, they still represent a minority of all entrepreneurs. Women entrepreneurs often face many problems in starting and growing their businesses even though there are some successful names in women entrepreneurship in India. Successful women entrepreneurs consider their problems as a step to success and innovation. They take these problems as a challenge and face it boldly, instead of running away from it. Indira Nooyi, Kiran Mazumdar shaw, Naina Lal Kidwai, Vaidya Manohar Chhabria, Neelam Dhawan, Shahnaz Husain, Lalita Gupte, Ekta Kappor are some names of successful women in their respective fields. Following table shows women entrepreneurship in India.

Table 1.1 Women Entrepreneurship in India

S.No	States	No. of units Registered	No. of women Entrepreneurs	Percentage
1	Tamil Nadu	9618	2930	30.36
2	Gujarat	3872	1538	39.72
3	Karnataka	3822	1026	26.84
4	Kerala	5487	2135	38.91
5	Maharashtra	4339	1394	32.12
6	Madhya Pradesh	2967	842	28.38
7	Punjab	4791	1618	33.77
8	Uttar Pradesh	7980	3180	39.84
9	Other States & UTS	14576	4185	28.71
TOTAL		57,452	18,848	32.82

Source: MSME Census Reports

It is clear from the above mentioned table 1.1 reveals that there are 18,848 women entrepreneurs in India, Uttar Pradesh rank first with 39.84 per cent followed by Gujarat with 39.72 per cent. Kerala, Punjab and Maharashtra are some other states having good number of women entrepreneurs. Overall percentage of women entrepreneurs in India is 32.82 %. There is a need of increase in women entrepreneurship in India.

Associations of Women Entrepreneurs

With the growth of Entrepreneurship in the country a few associations of women Entrepreneurs have emerged to work for and to create a congenial atmosphere for the development of Entrepreneurship in urban and rural areas. These associations are:

- Women Entrepreneurs wing of National Alliance of young Entrepreneurs.
- Association of Women Entrepreneurs of Karnataka.
- Self-Employment Women Association of Ahmedabad.
- Indian Council of Women Entrepreneurs, New Delhi.
- FICCI Ladies Organization
- National Standing Committee on Women Entrepreneurs.
- Women Entrepreneurs Association of Tamilnadu.

Women Empowerment and Planning Process in India

The all round development of women has been one of the focal point of planning process in India. The First Five-Year Plan (1951-56) envisaged a number of welfare measures for women. Establishment of the Central Social Welfare Board, organization of Mahila Mandals and the Community Development Programmes were a few steps in this direction. In the Second Five-Year Plan (1956-61), the empowerment of women was closely linked with the overall approach of intensive agricultural development programmes. The Third and Fourth Five-Year Plans (1961-66 and 1969-74) supported female education as a major welfare measure. The Fifth Five-Year Plan (1974-79) emphasized training of women, who were in need of income and protection. This plan coincided with International Women's Decade and the submission of Report of the Committee on the Status of Women in India. In 1976, Women's welfare and Development Bureau was set up under the Ministry of Social Welfare. The Sixth Five-Year Plan (1980-85) saw a definite shift from welfare to development. It recognized women's lack of access to resources as a critical factor impeding their growth. The Seventh Five-Year Plan (1985-90) emphasized the need for gender equality and empowerment. For the first time, emphasis was placed upon qualitative aspects such as inculcation of confidence, generation of awareness with regards, to rights and training in skills for better employment. The Eight Five-Year Plan (1992-97) focused on empowering women, especially at the grass roots level, through Panchayati Raj Institutions. The Ninth Five-Year Plan (1997-2002) adopted a strategy of women's component plan, under which not less than 30 percent of funds/benefits were earmarked for women-specific programmes. The Tenth Five-Year Plan (2002-07) aims at empowering women through translating the recently adopted National Policy for Empowerment of Women (2001) into action and ensuring Survival, Protection and Development of women and children through rights based approach. The Eleventh Five-Year Plan lays down six monitorable targets (1) Raise the sex ratio for age group 0-6 from 927 in 2001 to 935 by 2011-12 and to 950 by 2016-17; (2) Ensure that at least 33% of the direct and indirect beneficiaries of all government schemes are women and girl children; (3) Reduce IMR from 57 to 28 and MMR from 3.01 to one per 1000 live births; (4) 51 Reduce malnutrition among children of age group 0-3 to half its present level; (5) Reduce anaemia among women and girls by 50% by the end of the Eleventh Plan; and (6) Reduce dropout rate for primary and secondary schooling by 10% for both girls as well as boys." (See Appendix).

Problems Encountered by Women Entrepreneurs in India

Women entrepreneurs encounter two sets of problems, viz, general problems of entrepreneurs and problems specific to women entrepreneurs.

These are discussed as follows:

- **Problem of finance:** Finance is regarded as “life blood” for any enterprise, be it big or small. However, women entrepreneurs suffer from shortage of finance on two counts. **Firstly**, women do not generally have property on their names to use them as collateral for obtaining funds from external sources. Thus, their access to the external sources of funds is limited. **Secondly**, the banks also consider women less credit-worthy and discourage women borrowers on the belief that they can at any time leave their business. Given such situation, women entrepreneurs are bound to rely on their own savings, if any and loans from friends and relatives who are expectedly meager and negligible. Thus, women enterprises fail due to the shortage of finance.
- **Scarcity of raw material:** Most of the women enterprises are plagued by the scarcity of raw material and necessary inputs. Added to this are the high prices of raw material, on the other. The failure of nay women co- operatives in 1971 engaged in basket making is an example how the scarcity of raw material sounds the dearth- knell of enterprises run by women.
- **Stiff Competition:** Women entrepreneurs do not have organization set- up to pump in a lot of money for canvassing and advertisement. Thus, they have to face a stiff competition for marketing their products with both organized sector and their male counterparts. Such a competition ultimately results in the liquidation of women enterprises.
- **Limited Mobility:** Unlike men, women mobility in India is highly limited due to various reasons. A single woman asking for room is still upon suspicion. Cumbersome exercise involved in starting an enterprise coupled with the officials humiliating attitude towards women compels them to give up an idea of starting an enterprise.
- **Family Ties:** In India, it is mainly a woman’s duty to look after the children and other members of the family. Man plays a secondary role only. In case of married woman, she has to strike a fine balance between her business and family. Her total involvement in family leaves little or no energy and time to devote for business. Support and approval of husbands seem necessary condition or women’s entry in to business. Accordingly, the educational level and family background of husbands positively influence women’s entry into business activities.
- **Lack of Education:** In India, around three- fifths (60%) of women are still illiterate illiteracy is the root cause of socio- economic problems. Due to the lack of education and that too qualitative education, women are not aware of business, technology and market knowledge. Also, lack of education cases low achievement motivation among women. Thus, lack of education creates problems for women in the setting up and running of business enterprises.
- **Male dominated Society:** Male chauvinism is till the order of the day in India. The constitution of India speaks of equality between sexes. But, in practice women are looked upon as **able i.e.** weak in all respects. Women suffer from male reservations about a women’s role, ability and capacity and are treated accordingly. In nutshell, in the male dominated Indian society, women are not treated equal to men. This in turn, serves as a barrier to women entry into business.
- **Low Risk- Bearing Ability:** Women in India lead a protected life. They are less educated and economically not self- dependent. All these reduce their ability to bear risk involved in running an enterprise. Risk bearing is an essential requisite of a successful entrepreneur. In addition to above problems, inadequate infra structural facilities, shortage of power, high cost of production, social attitude, low need for achievement and socio- economic constraints also hold the women back from entering into business. Indian women entrepreneurs are facing major problems like, financial assistance, lack of confidence in their strength and competence, socio-cultural barriers, market- oriented risks, motivational factors, knowledge in Business administration, awareness about the financial assistance, exposed to the training programs, identifying the available resources and problems at family level. Some problems faced by women entrepreneurs in India are as follows.

Policies and Schemes Initiated by the Government towards Women Entrepreneurs in India

Development of women has been a policy objective of the government since independence. Women were given priorities in all the sectors. Government and non government bodies have paid increasing attention towards women contribution through self employment and

industrial ventures. In India, the Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises development organizations, various State Small Industries Development Corporations, the nationalized banks and even NGOs are conducting various programmes to cater to the needs of potential women entrepreneurs, who may not have adequate educational background and skills. There are several schemes of the government at central and state level, which provide assistance for setting up training-cum-income generating activities for needy women to make them economically independent. In addition to this there are certain special incentives and concessions for women entrepreneurs. At present, the Government announces many schemes for women entrepreneurs in India. Some of these are as follows.

- Integrated Rural Development Programs (IRDP), Training of Rural youth for self-employment (TRYSEM) etc. were started to alleviate poverty. 30-40% reservation was provided to women under this scheme.
- Prime minister Rojar Yojana and EDPs were introduced to develop entrepreneurial qualities among rural women.
- Rashtriya Mahila Kosh was set up to grant micro credit to poor women at reasonable rates of interest with very low transaction costs and simple procedures.
- The Ministry of small Industries launched 'Trade Related Entrepreneurship Assistance and Development' (TREAD) scheme to develop women entrepreneurs across the country, in rural, semi-urban and urban areas by developing entrepreneurial qualities and skills.
- The government introduced two schemes - 'Swarna Jayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana, and Swaran Jayanti Sahakari Rozgar Yojana' to encourage women to start their own business ventures and to provide reservations for women.
- State Industrial and Development Bank of India (SIDBI) introduced a number of schemes to assist the women entrepreneurs, viz., Mahila Udyam Nidhi, Micro Credit Scheme for Women, Mahila Vikas Nidhi, Entrepreneurship Development Programmes for women, and Marketing Development Fund for Women.
- The government too initiated two schemes for training women entrepreneurs through specialized institutions, especially, towards self-employment - Support for Training and Employment Programme of Women (STEP) and Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas (DWCRA).
- Special strategy for the Women Component Plan was formulated to ensure that at least 30% of funds and benefits flow to women from all development sectors. Self-help groups were devised as a mark of the beginning of empowering women.
- During the Eleventh Plan, it was planned to revamp the scheme for skill development of women, Support to Training and Employment Programme (STEP), and to integrate it with two schemes - Swayamsidha, an existing scheme for holistic empowerment of women through SHGs, to ensure adequate outlay and Rashtriya Mahila Kosh for credit Linkages. Enabling participation of women entrepreneurs in 25 international exhibitions was scheduled to provide them marketing incentives.
- The Schemes promoting women empowerment/ entrepreneurship for the XII Plan period include Support to Training and Employment Programme (STEP), priyadarshini Scheme, Micro-Credit Scheme of Rastriya Mahila Kosh. The national mission for Empowerment of Women (NMEW) was launched on 8th March 2010 with a view to empowering women socially, economically and educationally.

Suggestions

It is clear that even though there are sufficient schemes and support from government for the development of women entrepreneurs, they are not stepping forward to take benefit of it. Here are some suggestive measures, to solve the problems faced by them and for running their enterprise smoothly.

- Based on this study, the researcher recommends that Government should design specific training programmes to impart latest technologies and skills for self-development.
- As a motivational measure, educational institutions may be given the duty of identifying potential entrepreneurs and recommend the same to the Government to issue financial assistance.

- Success stories of women entrepreneurs from varied back- grounds should be popularized through various media.
- Education is a must to inculcate the spirit of equality in Women.
- Women must be encouraged to actively participate in debates/seminars/conferences and should be told that there is no shortcut to success; particularly the Entrepreneurial path requires sacrifice, diligence and devotion.
- Inclusion of Entrepreneurship development as a compulsory subject in the school curriculum itself. Guidance and counseling cells in Universities and Colleges also need to be established for educating women about the benefits of an Entrepreneurial career.
- Training centers should provide training to prospective women Entrepreneurs free of cost and Entrepreneurial development programmes should be much more practical-oriented.
- Inculcation of self-confidence amongst women that they also can run a business should be one of the prime motives of these programmes.
- Potential women Entrepreneurs should be exposed to different types of emerging opportunities.
- There should be a continuous attempt to inspire, encourage, motivate and cooperate women entrepreneurs.
- An Awareness programme should be conducted on a mass scale with the intention of creating awareness among women about the various areas to conduct business.
- Attempts should be there to enhance the standards of education of women in general as well making effective provisions for their training, practical experience and personality development programmes, to improvise their over-all personality standards.
- Organize training programmes to develop professional competencies in managerial, leadership, marketing, financial, production process, profit planning, maintaining books of accounts and other skills. This will encourage women to undertake business.
- Vocational training to be extended to women community that enables them to understand the production process and production management.
- Educational institutes should tie up with various government and non-government agencies to assist in entrepreneurship development mainly to plan business projects.
- International, National, Local trade fairs, Industrial exhibitions, seminars and conferences should be organized to help women to facilitate interaction with other women entrepreneurs.
- Women in business should be offered soft loans & subsidies for encouraging them into industrial activities. The financial institutions should provide more working capital assistance both for small scale venture and large scale ventures.
- Making provision of micro credit system and enterprise credit system to the women entrepreneurs at local level.
- Provide business training to women.
- Provide guidance in balancing family work responsibilities.
- Amounts loan are frequent short duration and charge nominal rate of interest.

Conclusion

The emergence of women entrepreneurs and their contribution to the national economy is quite visible in India. The glass ceilings are shattered and women are found to be indulged in every line of business from papad to power cables. Even though we have many successful Women Entrepreneurs in our country, but as we have a male dominated culture there are many challenges which women entrepreneurs face from family & Society. Even though we have many successful women entrepreneurs in our country, still the situation is disappointing one. At this juncture, effective steps are needed to provide entrepreneurial awareness, orientation and special skill development programs to women. The role of Women entrepreneur in economic development is also being recognized and steps are being taken to promote women entrepreneurship. From these suggestions it is quite visible that for development and promotion of women entrepreneurship, in the region, there is a need for multi dimensional approach from different sector, namely from the government side, financial institutions, individual women entrepreneurs

and many more, for a flexible integrated and coordinated specific approach. The principal factor in developing entrepreneurship among women is not in terms of infrastructure or financial assistance or identifying an enterprise but it is a question of clearing the ground for their movement into entrepreneurship. Though there are several factors contributing to the emergence of women as entrepreneurs, the sustained and coordinated effort from all dimensions would pave the way for the women moving into entrepreneurial activity thus contributing to the social and economic development of the members of the family and thereby gaining equality and equal importance for themselves.

References

1. Bharati Collen and Indira Parikh (August 2005), „A Reflection of Indian Women In the Entrepreneurial World., Indian Institute of Management, Ahmadabad, Working paper Number 2005-08-07.
2. Bhatia Anju (2000) “Women Development and NGOs”. Rawat Publication, New Delhi.
3. David H .Holt (2003), „Entrepreneurship New Venture Creation., prentice-Hall India.
4. Gordon E. & Natarajan K.: (2007): ‘Entrepreneurship Development’, Himalaya Publication House, Second Revised edition, Mumbai.
5. Hattangadi V, (2007), „Entrepreneurship -Need of the hour. Himalaya Publishing House.
6. Helene Ahl “Why Research on Women Entrepreneurs Needs New Directions”, Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice Volume 30 Issue 5.
7. Lalita .N, (2005): ‘Micro Finance and Rural Development’, Gandhi gram Rural Institute, Gandhi gram, Dindigal, Tamilnadu.
8. Ram Naresh Thakur (2009): ‘Rural Women Empowerment in India’ in Empowerment of Rural Women in India, Kanishka Publishers, New Delhi.
9. Rani D. L. (1996): ‘Women Entrepreneurs’, APH Publishing House, New Delhi.
10. Singh Kamala. (1992): ‘Women entrepreneurs’, Ashish publishing house, New Delhi.
11. Zubair M. (2003): ‘Empowering Rural Women: An Approach to Empowering Women through Credit-Based Self Help Groups’, Aakar Books, Delhi.
12. Nayyar, Pooja et. al. (2007), “Causes and Constraints Faced by Women Entrepreneurs in Entrepreneurial Process”, The Journal of Social Science., 14(2): 99-102.
13. Punitha. M. Sangeetha, S. Padmavathi (1999), “Women Entrepreneurs: Their problems and constraints”, Indian Journal of Labour Economics, Vol 42, No: 4, p 701-706.
14. Rathore, B.S. and Chabra, Rama (1991), “Promotion of Women Entrepreneurship- Training Strategies”, SEDME.
15. Reddi, P.N. (1991), “Problems of Women Entrepreneurs in Goa: A pilot study”. Khadi Gramodyog, 37(4): 157-159.
16. Singh K.P (1993), “Women Entrepreneurs: Their Profile and Motivation”, The Journal of Entrepreneurship, 2, 1.